
The Importance of the Different Types in Tourism

Kobilova Maftuna Khalilovna

Lecturer at “SilkRoad” International university of tourism and cultural heritage

***Annotation.** For hospitality workers like you understanding that a lot of types of tourism exist is crucial to promoting your accommodation and your area in the right way. It's as important to know who is your targets and buyer personas are in order to build the perfect strategy to attract them.*

***Keywords:** domestic tourism, international tourism, guests, outbound tourism, inbound tourism.*

INTRODUCTION

What are the 3 main types of tourism?

What is inbound tourism?

Inbound tourism is the golden egg-laying goose of the tourist industry. It's when people come from their own countries to visit and spend their foreign currency on tours and accommodations. While it may not be strictly sustainable – just ask the seaside spots in 2020 – this **type of tourism** is as vital a part of the tourism industry as suitcases. Without it popular destinations like Italy, Paris, and New York are just cities. If you want to boost your local economy and your own financial well-being by default then you want as much inbound tourism as possible.

What is domestic tourism?

With the pandemic making international travel a challenging prospect citizens are choosing to explore their own nations instead. Not only is domestic tourism cost-effective, but it also allows travellers to explore landscapes or historical sites that they may have overlooked before.

And let's not forget the joy of experiencing your own culture and community all the while indulging in food tourism that reminds you of your grandmother's cooking. These are the kinds of experiences that create lasting memories and make travellers want to come back for more giving you the possibility to

gain your guests' loyalty – an authentic blessing when it comes to direct bookings and revenue in general.

What is outbound tourism?

Outbound tourism refers to the activity of people traveling outside of their country of residence for the purpose of tourism. It involves booking tours, reserving accommodations, and spending money on various tourist activities in a foreign country. Outbound tourism is a significant part of the tourism industry and can have a significant impact on the economies of both the traveler's country of residence and the destination country.

Which types of tourism are popular?

1) Health and wellness tourism

This **type of tourism** is gaining more and more popularity with the general societal increase in concerns over mental health. Health and wellness tourism refers to a type of travel where individuals seek to improve their physical, mental, or emotional well-being through various activities and experiences. This can include visiting destinations that offer health and wellness programs, such as yoga retreats, spas, or wellness resorts, or engaging in activities like hiking, meditation, or nutrition workshops. The focus of this **type of tourism** is on promoting personal health and well-being, rather than simply sightseeing or entertainment.

Marketing tips for health and wellness tourism

If you have a spa or your hotel is close to the mountains, for example, you should promote those particular characteristics by speaking about them on your website by way of a blog article or speaking out about all the benefits your amenities and those of your surrounding area can give to anyone looking for relaxation and simply a break. You could also publicise a special offer on social media or your website for the World Mental Health Day.

2) Countryside tourism

This one is exactly what it says on the tin. Travellers visit remote areas in order to get a taste of something simpler – often for cheaper than anything is available in the big city.

This **type of tourism** isn't as rooted in tours or tourist attractions so much as others. It is more concerned with the the visitor experience. It's about escaping from one's usual environment and experiencing life as other people live it, away from the noise of the hoi polloi. Oftentimes, countryside tourism is about experiencing an event as opposed to seeing some great thing or exploring some particular environment. These types of events are listed by Unesco – the united nation world tourism collective – alongside famous buildings and cities, so you know we're serious.

Marketing tips for countryside tourism

This **type of tourism** it's also called rural tourism and it's a great for guest houses and B&Bs in particular. People love to taste ancient flavours and breath clean air in a pure background. Be sure to broadcast every detail on your website and on your social media posts. Convey closeness from texts to photos. Do you have a pet running around the property? Show it off! Do you have funny family stories that happened on the property? Tell them. Do you have a small vegetable garden or a garden? Take photos and post them on social media. Do you provide bikes? Well, what are you waiting for to post it on social media or give discounts to your loyal customers?

3) Business tourism

This **type of tourism** involves travelling to different locations to attend to business issues or work. In business tourism, individuals still work according to their regular schedule, but the difference is they are doing it away from their typical workplaces. Examples of activities that happen in business travel include attending seminars, trade fairs, meetings, conferences – that kind of thing. Business tourism doesn't involve tours, per se, but it does involve booking into a hotel and eating and spending money in the local community and so it appears on this list.

Marketing tips for business tourism

A great idea? Keep up to speed with all the trade fairs and events in your city and in your area. As a general rule it is important to have a comprehensive vision of everything happening in your area and to use whatever there is from one week to the next to favourably augment your Occupancy Rate. Needless to say – if you have a conference room in your structure you should make this element evident on your website, giving all the information that an organiser might need from prices to numbers of seats to the possibility of adding a buffet.

4) Food tourism

Speaking of buffets – there anyone who doesn't love good food? Many tourists simply follow their taste buds and choose their holiday destinations based on the things they want to eat. Popular destinations for food tourism include Italy, Spain, France, and Japan and if you're in any one of these destinations or a particular location that's known for nice food that I haven't named just make sure your marketing includes a picture of whatever's local and delicious. It's what I call "a delicious **type of tourism**"

Marketing tips for food tourism

Share tips on places to eat local food, take vineyard tours and "foody" entertainment like that. You can partner with a local chef or workshop to teach how to prepare a local delicacy. Make upselling your workhorse with local delicacies and make deals with local restaurants to offer discounts to your customers (discounts, needless to say, must be well publicised).

5) Sports tourism

Sports tourism is a **type of tourism** that involves attending sporting events or participating in sports activities. As a hotelier, sports tourism presents an opportunity to attract a specific kind of traveller and to increase occupancy during periods of high demand. Sports events, such as marathons, golf tournaments, and international sporting competitions, can draw large numbers of visitors to a destination. These travellers often require accommodations, making hotels a key part of the sports tourism industry.

Marketing tips for sport tourism

Be sure to be always aware of all the sports event in your city and even in your area at large. Sometimes a good price can convince people to sleep in a nearby location. Be smart and play always with dynamic pricing to have always a competitive price. Amenitiz PriceAdvisor gives you the possibility to set competitive prices compared to your competitors and your past demand, to always have a high occupation rate.

Advertise always when you can offer specialised services and amenities, such as early breakfast options for athletes, secure storage for sports equipment, and fitness facilities. These services can help to differentiate a hotel from its competitors and attract sports tourists.

6) Wildlife tourism

Wildlife tourism is a growing industry that involves travelling to natural areas to observe and interact with wildlife. This can include activities such as birdwatching, whale watching, and safaris. Hotels located near national parks or other protected areas can also benefit from wildlife tourism, as these areas are often home to a wide variety of animals that tourists may want to see.

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